

Effectiveness of Teachers in North Lombok Regency's Public High Schools: The Impact of Competency and Leadership

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to investigate how competency and leadership among North Lombok Regency's State High School Teachers affect their effectiveness as teachers. This kind of study uses a quantitative method and is causal associative in nature. Using a proportionate random selection approach, 295 instructors at North Lombok Regency State High School were the total number of respondents chosen for the sample, which resulted in 75 responses overall. PLS-SEM data analysis was performed using Smart PLS 3 software. The study's findings demonstrated that, at North Lombok Regency State High School, competency had a positive and substantial impact on teachers' performance while leadership had a favorable but negligible impact. The results of this research are proof that it is very necessary to increase competency, therefore State High School teachers in North Lombok Regency are expected.

Keywords:- Competence, Leadership, Teacher Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources have an important role in achieving organizational goals, because humans always play an active and dominant role in every organizational activity, both as planners and implementers (Samsuni, 2017). According to Dessler, (2017), human resources can also be interpreted as resources that can be developed and managed to achieve organizational goals. If human resources are good then the existence of the organization in the future will be good, human resources are said to be good if they have high performance at work, and conversely, if human resources are bad then the running of the organization will be bad, because bad human resources have a level of low performance. To provide good personnel, high employee performance is highly expected by the company. The more workers who have superior performance, the general efficiency of the organization will increase with the aim that the organization can survive in world competition (Aswan & Yandiana, 2023). In order for management activities in an organization to run well, the company must have employees who are knowledgeable and highly skilled and strive to manage the company as optimally as possible so that employee performance increases.

Performance is the measure of a job well done, or the difference between actual output and predetermined benchmarks (Dessler, 1992). Performance, according to Robbins & Judge (2017), is the outcome of a job when an individual satisfies certain requirements relevant to that position. This might include completing tasks on time, delivering high-quality work, or abiding by corporate regulations. According to the above statement, each employee's performance is determined by the outcomes of their labor. In assessing teacher performance, Uno & Nina (2014: 71-72), teacher performance has five dimensions, namely, (1) quality of work, (2) speed/accuracy of work, (3) initiative in work, and (4) ability to communicate work.

Various factors can impact the degree of performance that employees provide. Gibson (2006) asserts that individual, psychological, and organizational elements are the three main determinants of an employee's success, whereas Robbins (2017) lists ability, motivation, and opportunity as the three aspects influencing an employee's performance. According to Duha (2018), there are additional factors that affect employee performance, including physical environment, organizational climate, conflict, organizational commitment, and organizational effectiveness. Additionally, there are factors like motivation, organizational culture, leadership, work procedures, communication, level of education, work experience, compensation, training, career development, and promotion. Workplace motivation, education and training (competency), remuneration, technology, skills, and work discipline are the elements that affect performance, according to Anoraga (2017:178). From the factors mentioned above, researchers want to examine competency factors as factors originating from individuals and/or employee ability factors, then leadership factors which are elements of the organization.

Competency is a skill that enables someone to do a job or function based on their knowledge and abilities, with the help of the actions required by their line of work (Mulia & Saputra, 2020). The ability to communicate and apply knowledge and insight in a new setting while increasing the agreed-upon advantages is one aspect of competence, which is defined as a person's capacity to create at a sufficient level in the sphere of activity (Syah et al., 2021). According to Lubis et al. (2019), competency is the ability of a person to do a task accurately and with excellence in circumstances involving

actions, knowledge, and abilities that will affect his performance. The indicators for measuring competence according to (Kanafiah et al., 2021; Syafitri et al., 2021) are technical skills, knowledge, mastery of technology, work skills, and communication.

Suhardi (2019) performed a study at PT. Life Insurance in Batam City with support from earlier studies on the impact of competency on employee performance. The findings of the research indicate that competency has a substantial impact on employee performance. Then, at the major intellectual education foundation in Surabaya, Ashar et al. (2019) carried out the study, and the findings showed that competence had a favorable and substantial impact on worker performance. Additionally, a study by Arlita et al. (2020) in a junior high school in the Prabumulih sub-district revealed a relationship between competency and teacher effectiveness. On the other hand, a study by Setyanti (2020) claimed that employee performance is not much impacted by competence. Thus, there is a research void in this study and further testing needs to be done.

According to Yukl (2009), leadership is the ability to persuade people of the importance of a task and the best way to do it, as well as the facilitation of both individual and group efforts toward the achievement of shared objectives. In essence, Thoah (2010) states that leadership is the capacity to affect other people's conduct, whether or not it takes place in an official organization. This shows that leadership can occur in any context, as long as someone shows the ability to guide others toward certain goals (Hermanto et al., 2023). Path-Goal Theory was developed by Robert House in 1971, path-goal theory cites elements from research on leadership. This theory suggests that it is the leader's job to provide information, support, or other resources for followers to achieve goals. The stated aim of this leadership theory is to improve employee performance (Rahmawati et al., 2023). The indicators for measuring leadership according to Kartono, (2016) are (1) the ability to make decisions, (2) the ability to motivate, (3) the communication ability, (4) the ability to control subordinates, and (5) the ability to control emotions.

Leadership is considered very important because it relates to efforts to achieve institutional goals through influencing other people within the institution (Fayzhall et al., 2020). With good leadership, motivation and job satisfaction will be created for a company's employees. Motivating is a desire that moves someone to do something. This means that leaders help motivate subordinates to be more stable at work. Guiding subordinates are expected to be able to make efforts to understand, accept and provide services to solve problems experienced by subordinates (Gistituati, & Rusdinal, 2021). According to earlier studies by Jayanti & Wati (2020) and Efitriana & Liana (2022), leadership significantly and favorably affects worker performance. This demonstrates that capable leaders may promote higher performance within a group or company and validates the idea that superior performance can be a result of good leadership. This, however, contradicts the findings of a study by Wibowo & Syafii (2023) which found no relationship between leadership and worker performance. There is currently a study gap on the

link between these factors, thus more thorough investigation is required.

A study on teacher performance related to competency and leadership was carried out at all Senior High Schools (SMA) in North Lombok Regency. Research across high schools regarding competency and leadership on teacher performance is very important because this has a direct impact on the quality of education. Teachers have a major role in providing effective learning to students. By understanding teacher competency and leadership in depth, schools can identify strengths and weaknesses in teacher performance, as well as areas where improvement is needed. This allows schools to take appropriate action, such as providing additional training, establishing professional development programs, or evaluating school leadership practices. Thus, this research helps increase teacher effectiveness, improve the quality of education, and create a more satisfying work environment for educators, all of which have a positive impact on student development and the progress of the education system, especially in North Lombok Regency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Teacher Performance

Whitmore (1997), simply stated that performance is the implementation of the functions required of a person. According to Whitmore, understanding is an understanding that requires the minimum requirements for success. Therefore, Whitmore put forward the definition of performance which is considered representative, so that it depicts the great responsibility of a person's work (Uno & Nina, 2014). Based on the definition above, a real performance that far exceeds what is expected is a performance that sets the person's own highest standards, always standards that exceed what other people ask or expect (Uni & Nina, 2014). Thus, according to Whitmore, performance is an action, an achievement, or what someone shows through real skills (Whitmore, 1997). Performance demands the expression of one's potential, and overall responsibility or ownership (Uno & Nina, 2014:60). Uno & Lina (2014:61) cited an alternative viewpoint that defines performance as an individual's activity in completing the primary responsibilities allocated to them. With reference to this perspective, it may be understood that an individual's productivity is correlated with the daily activities they do. For instance, he carries out the teaching and learning process at school as part of his regular duties as a teacher. The performance of a teacher is the best outcome attained from the teaching activity. Unlike Simon (1994), he believes that an individual's motivation, ability, and perception interact or operate to produce their performance.

B. Competence

Competence, according to Boulter et al. (in Rosidah, 2003:11), is a fundamental quality of a person that empowers workers to deliver exceptional performance in their profession. According to the aforementioned definition, competence is defined as having a strong personality and being a person who consistently behaves in a predictable manner under a variety of conditions and during tasks. The

standards or criteria applied can be used to predict who would do better and worse. Competence, according to Spencer and Spencer (in Moeheriono, 2009:3), is the fundamental quality of a person that is related to how well they perform at work or to the fundamental traits of a person that are causally related to or have an effect on the criteria that are used as a reference, effective or excellent performance or superior at work or in certain situations.

C. Leadership

According to Davis et al. (1995), leadership is the capacity to inspire people to pursue their objectives with zeal. According to Gibson (1982), management is a broader notion than leadership. The style of leadership a person uses will have a big impact on how they try to persuade others or get them to do as they are instructed. Conversely, leadership, as defined by Davis et al. (1995), is the leader's general behavior pattern as seen by his subordinates. According to Yukl (2013), leadership is the ability to persuade people, comprehend and concur on what has to be done and how it should be done, and support both individual and group efforts to accomplish shared objectives. To effectively implement certain aspects of their leadership, leaders must first have a thorough understanding of the people they lead, their strengths and weaknesses, and how to best leverage their subordinates' strengths to offset their weaknesses (Ainanur, 2013).

D. The Influence of Competency on Performance

The opinion of Lubis et al., (2019) is that competence is an employee's skill to carry out a job correctly and has excellence based on conditions involving knowledge, skills, and actions that will influence his performance. Competence is a person's characteristic that can be demonstrated through knowledge, skills and behavior that can produce performance and achievement (Dessler, 2017:70). Measurable competencies are the core of the performance management process which can be observed and applied critically for the success of an organization and work performance as well as employee's personal contributions to the organization (Wibowo, 2016: 86). This will provide a strong incentive for employees to carry out the tasks assigned to them efficiently, effectively and psychologically. The research results of Manani and Ngui (2019), and Yunanda (2019), state that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, this is in line with research conducted by Martini, et al., (2020), Zefanya (2020), Pangaribuan and Sihombing (2021), and Yulius (2022) who explain that there is a positive and significant influence between employee competence and performance. Based on the explanation above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H1: Competency has a positive and significant effect on the performance of high school teachers in North Lombok Regency

E. The Influence of Leadership on Performance

Leaders are expected to be able to carry out their functions to mobilize and direct their subordinates to carry out their work duties. In completing tasks, superiors not only give work to subordinates, but superiors also participate in supervising and completing work on company tasks. With the workload, namely hard and firm targets and leadership, this

will make employees feel pressured so that the results of employee performance decrease. To create harmonious working relationships, a leader is needed who can have a big influence and can motivate his employees (Mutuya et al., 2022). Leadership is considered very important because it relates to efforts to achieve institutional goals through influencing other people within the institution (Fayzhall et al., 2020). With good leadership, motivation and job satisfaction will be created for employees. Motivating is a desire that moves someone to do something. This means that leaders help motivate subordinates to be more stable at work. Guiding subordinates is expected to be able to make efforts to understand, receive and provide services to solve problems experienced by subordinates (Gistituati, & Rusdinal, 2021). Supported by previous research conducted by Jayanti & Wati, (2020); Efitriana & Liana, (2022); Silahusada et al., (2022); and Fajeri, (2023) that leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This indicates that leaders with leadership are able to encourage improved performance in a team or organization, and also confirms that effective leadership can contribute to better performance. Based on the explanation above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of high school teachers in North Lombok Regency

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative method and is associative in nature. In North Lombok Regency, this study was carried out in every state high school. In this study, 75 individuals made up the sample, all of them were state high school teachers in the North Lombok Regency. A subset or representative of the population under study is the sample (Arikunto, 2010). According to Sugiyono (2014), the sampling strategy used in this study is a probability sampling strategy, which means that every component of the population has an equal chance of being chosen at random to be a part of the sample, regardless of the public's strata. Data was obtained by a questionnaire that used a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The items in the questionnaire consist of thirty-six statement types. This was followed by an analysis of the study data utilizing the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) and PLS 3.0 smart software.

IV. RESULTS

This outer loading is used to describe how well the items reflect or describe the measurement of the variable. Rule of thumb according to Chin, (1998), an outer loading value > 0.50 is acceptable (valid).

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Influence of Competency on Teacher Performance

The results of this research show that Spiritual Leadership has Based on figure 4.1 and table 4.11, the results show that the path coefficient is 0.327; t-count 2.05; and p value of 0.028. It can be stated that competency has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, so that the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted. This means that if a teacher's competence is more appropriate or higher, then the teacher's performance will increase. On the other hand, if a teacher's competence becomes less appropriate or lower, then the teacher's performance will decrease. In determining organizational policies, especially in the field of education, it is necessary to prioritize meeting needs in terms of increasing competence for teachers which will have an impact on increasing motivation and emphasizing performance levels (Sugiono et al., 2022). Mutakin (2015), that the performance produced by teachers is influenced by the competencies they have. The role of teachers is very important in schools so that teachers are expected to have competence as a driver to produce performance as educators. This was also stated by Mukhtar (2018) that good competence will increase good work results.

According to the respondent's answer in the competency category, the item "Having a high level of competence and trying to keep up with existing developments" is the answer with the highest score, this shows that an integral part of the educational process focuses on student learning. To achieve optimal educational outcomes, teachers must have strong competence in the subjects they teach and also in effective teaching methods. Awareness of the importance of these competencies encourages them to strive to acquire and maintain a high level of knowledge and skills. Additionally, the world of education continues to change with technological developments, new research, and changing societal demands. Teachers who are committed to following these developments will be better prepared to face changes in the curriculum, teaching methods, and new challenges that arise in the world of education. The results of this research are in line with those conducted by Utami et al., (2022); Zulfahami et al., (2022); and Lestari et al., (2023) show that competence has a significant effect on teacher performance and competence also has a simultaneous or partial effect on teacher performance.

B. The Influence of Leadership on Teacher Performance

Based on figure 4.1 and table 4.11, the results show that the path coefficient is 0.165; t-count 1.396; and p value of 0.163. It can be stated that leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on teacher performance, so the second hypothesis (H2) is rejected. This means that even though the principal's leadership is being implemented more effectively, it cannot influence the increase in teacher performance, moreover, the principal's leadership itself is less effective, the principal's way of leading does not have a significant influence on teacher performance in North Lombok Regency Public High Schools. Implementing leadership activities that put more pressure on teachers may cause a teacher to achieve a certain level of performance in carrying out their work activities, but it may not necessarily have a positive influence

Fig 1. Path Coefficient

Tabel 1. Panel Data Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Relationship Between Variabel	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
Competence -> teacher performance	0,327	2,205	0,028
Leadership -> teacher performance	0,165	1,396	0,163

Sources: Research Data, 2023

Based on Figure 1 and Table 1 above, the relationship between variables (hypothesis test results) can be explained as follows:

- Competence has a significant positive effect on teacher performance with a coefficient value of 0.327, a t-statistic value of 2.205 > 1.96, and a P value of 0.028 < 0.05. So the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted. This means that the higher the competency a teacher has, the more significant the teacher's performance will be.
- Leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on teacher performance with a coefficient value of 0.165, a t statistic value of 1.396 < 1.96, and a P value of 0.163 > 0.05. So the second hypothesis (H2) is rejected. This means that the leadership possessed by a teacher does not have an influence on his performance.

in forming the personality of subordinates to work sincerely to achieve work goals (Sulistya, 2013). Each teacher has different characteristics, motivations and needs (Wulandari & Iriani, 2018). Some teachers may be more independent in carrying out their duties, while others may require more direct guidance and support from the principal. This individual variability can influence the extent to which the principal's leadership influences teacher performance (Yusmina et al., 2022).

In accordance with the respondent's answer in the leadership category in the item "The principal respects the opinions of employees even if it does not match his opinion" was the answer with the lowest score, meaning that the State High School teacher in Kab. North Lombok felt that this reflected teachers' distrust and dissatisfaction with school principals. When teachers feel that their opinions are not valued or considered important, this can create dissatisfaction which can negatively affect their performance. Additionally, effective leadership involves open, two-way communication between principals and teachers. If the principal does not effectively convey the reasons behind a decision or does not provide adequate explanations, teachers may feel they do not understand why the decision was made and thus lack the motivation to improve their performance. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Purwanto et al., (2020); Devinta & Santosa, (2022) show that leadership does not have a significant effect on teacher performance, meaning that the leadership style or way of leading a school principal does not have an influence on the work results or performance of a teacher because this performance is obtained from the efforts made.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Competence has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This means that if a teacher's competence is more appropriate or higher, then the teacher's performance will increase. On the other hand, if a teacher's competence becomes less appropriate or lower, then the teacher's performance will decrease. Besides that, it can be stated that leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on teacher performance. This means that, even though the principal's leadership is increasingly being carried out and implemented more effectively, it cannot influence the improvement of teacher performance, moreover the principal's leadership itself is less effectively implemented, and the way the principal leads does not have a significant influence on teacher performance.

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